

A Study to Examine the Attitude of Prospective Teachers towards Teaching Profession in Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 13, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: November 14, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Prospective Teachers, B.Ed., Teaching profession.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14166478</p>	<p><i>The study examined the attitude of the prospective teachers toward teaching as a profession. The population of this study comprised all B.Ed. students studying in teacher education institutes/department of Rawalpindi. A total of 200 students (N=200) were selected randomly from 10 institutes. A validated researchers' self-designed questionnaire was used for data collection. Primary data sources were used to approach the research-appropriate data. Quantitative research approach and descriptive survey design was used in the study. The data was analysed by descriptive and inferential statistics. t-test was used to compare both groups selected in the study. The outcomes of the study revealed that prospective teachers have negative attitude towards teaching as a profession. However, rural area's prospective teachers have significantly positive attitude to teaching as a profession than urban area's prospective teachers. In addition, female prospective teachers have significantly positive attitude towards teaching as a profession than male prospective teachers. Besides, recommendations are given in the paper for further information.</i></p>

Introduction

Teachers possess the focal position in a general public. No education framework can be superior without having the preeminent teachers. The potential and value of teachers decide the height to which education framework can rise. Excellence in education is call of the modern era. Quality education relies on the eminence of teachers as well as quality teachers can be delivered through quality educator education training programs (Cheema and Mehmood, 1997).

Teachers are the creator of our novel era. Unless we have the most devoted, committed and arranged educators in our instructive foundation, we cannot train incredible subjects for tomorrow. No arrangement of schooling can rise higher than the teachers who provide it. Its eminence is contingent in the long run on the attempts of the instructor. This subsequently relies on upon the reasonability with which they have been told by their own precise educators in the classrooms (Pakistan Educational Conference, 1983). The Report of the Commission on National Education (1959) perceived the requirement for scholastically competent and work wise prepared teachers as right on time as could be allowed, and suggested that the teacher ought to be scholastically all around prepared in the subject. Teachers must be professionally prepared to show their subject; have sound professional preparing in how to comprehend the kids in change; and have profound feeling of professional honour. (Sharif, Ministry of Education, Gov. of Pakistan., & Pakistan, 1960).

The study reflected that teachers are the cornerstones within the educational system. The behavioural patterns and traits are the major concerns that shape up the personal actions with the decision to choose a profession. Research on 300 prospective teachers has been conducted that showed insignificant differences in the attitude of pre-service teachers (Farooq, 1994).

A professional attitude is the feeling of a person, behaviours, and commitment to the profession. If teachers have a constructive attitude then their teaching efforts are fruitful. The outcomes showed that prospective teachers' attitude does not have any relationship with the variable such as religion, gender, locale, category, and a stream of research. The significant outcomes are seen in the attitude and academic qualification (Gage, 1983).

Research has investigated the prospective teachers' attitude to the teaching profession in terms of family income, gender, reasons to choose the teaching profession, and parental education. The study was conducted on the 146 prospective teachers that were designated through random sampling. The significant differences have been found on the prospective teachers to the teaching profession in standings of family income, gender, and educational level (Siddiqui, 1970).

The study developed an attitude to research (ATR) instrument administered on 277 graduates in varied programs. The outcomes showed that the final scale is based on the 27 items with different five subscales. The results indicated that the males and females have a parallel level of attitude towards the research, and significant differences have been found on the prospective teachers enrolled in different study programs (Siddiqui, 1986).

The research stated that the most important factor influence teachers' efficiency is an attitude towards the profession. The study was conducted on 117 participants at first, second, third, and fourth classes in the academic year 2008 to 2009. The study showed no significant differences on the attitude scores in terms of the effect of socio-economic level and class (Govt of Pakistan, 1977).

The 1947 Education Conference communicated apprehension about educator education and agreed revision of teacher education projects to make them good with evolving needs. Education assumed a to an inordinate degree fundamental part in an educational system approved, no system of education can be greater to anything the teachers who aid it (Ogunyinka, Okeke, & Adedoyin, (2015). The Commission suggested the supplementary scholastic and professional principles for educators of various norms.

The below table shows the teachers' level of qualification and extent of training required to each difference classes.

Table 1:

Teachers' required qualification for each class

Classes to Teach	Qualifications for Admission	Extent of Training
1-5	Matriculate	1 year
6-8	Intermediate	2 years
9-10	Bachelor's degree	2 years
11-12	Master's degree	A short training course

The teaching profession, all around, does not illustrate in the best talent in Pakistan. Those reflected fine either join the professions, for example, medicine and engineering and try to reposition toward the West or are dragged in by larger amount shared management positions, which exposed infrastructures for massive unite and exploitation (Okemakinde, Alabi, & Adewuyi, (2013). A couple of exceptions would be some exceptionally regarded education workforce and those researchers working at the most irregular amounts of the nation's inspection groundwork, mainly those included in increase rapidly and minute innovation.

Teacher Education in Pakistan is an imperative area for delve into. There is extensive text available on Education in Pakistan, which put forward, that the education system leaves much to be desired, predominantly in the vicinity of teacher education. In the paper, researchers examined the attitude of forthcoming teachers about teaching as an occupation.

Objectives

The study has following objectives:

1. To assess the attitude of the prospective teachers toward teaching as a profession.
2. To find out gender differences in the attitude of the prospective teachers toward teaching as a profession.
3. To find out rural urban differences in the attitude of the prospective teachers toward teaching as a profession.

Delimitations

- B.Ed. students studying in teacher education institutes/departments of Rawalpindi city.
- Year 2016

Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference in the attitude of rural and urban prospective teachers towards teaching as a profession.
- There is no significant difference in the attitude of male and female prospective teachers towards teaching as a profession.

Method

Research Design

Quantitative research approach and descriptive survey design was used in the study. The data was analysed by descriptive and inferential statistics. t-test was used to compare both groups selected in the study.

Sample

The population of the study was comprised of all B.Ed. students studying in teacher education institutes/department of Rawalpindi, Pakistan. At first, 10 institutes were selected randomly. Then a total of two hundred students ($N=200$) from each sampled institute) were randomly selected.

Measure

Questionnaire after pilot tested and then validated form was used as a research tool. A validated researchers' self-designed questionnaire was used for data collection. Data collected from this study was analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics (*t*-test statistical analysis).

Procedure

At first, 10 institutes were selected randomly. Then a total of two hundred students ($N=200$) from each sampled institute) were randomly selected. Test was established with the consent of the institute and the

teachers. The self-designed questionnaire was used after finding that it was a self-designed so permission from the author was not needed to use it. The informed consent from was given to the participants and the nature of study was explained to them before administration of questionnaire. Participants were assured about the confidentiality of information provided by them.

Ethical Considerations

In order to conduct this survey some ethical consideration was kept in mind. The self-designed questionnaire was used after finding that it was a self-designed so permission from the author was not needed to use it. The participants were approached personally and the principle of informed consent was strictly followed by the researcher, the researcher clearly described the scope of research to all participants and stated that all information provided would be anonymous and confidential.

Results

Many of the statistical procedures including correlation, regression, t tests, and analysis of variance, namely the parametric tests, are based on the assumption that the data follows a normal distribution (**Field, 2009**).

Table 2

Results of descriptive statistics of attitude of the prospective teachers toward teaching as a profession.

Variable	Number	Mean	SD	Minimum value	Maximum value	Range
Students' attitude towards teaching as a profession	200	38.74	13.56	15	75	60

Table 2 shows the results of descriptive statistics of undergraduate education students' attitude towards teaching as a profession. Minimum, maximum and range values were used to categorized students' responses as: 15-45 (Negative attitude), while 46-75 (Positive attitude). It is revealed from the table a mean score of 38.74 which fall within the range of negative attitude. This shows that prospective teacher's attitude towards teaching as a profession was not positive.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the attitude of rural and urban prospective teachers towards teaching as a profession

Table 3

t-test analysis of difference in the attitude of rural and urban prospective teachers towards teaching as a profession

Area	N	Mean	SD	Df	t -value
Rural	100	41.85	11.54	199	5.452*
Urban	100	35.63	7.28		

Significant at 0.05 level t -values at 0.05 = 2.029

Table 2 shows that the calculated t -value is 5.452 with significant probability value (p-value) of 0.000 computed at level of significance 0.05. Since the intended p-value of 0.000 is less than alpha level, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that significant differences exist in the attitude of rural and urban prospective teachers towards teaching as an occupation.

Hypothesis 2. There is no significant difference in the attitude of male and female prospective teachers towards teaching as a profession

Table 4

t-test analysis of difference in the attitude of male and female prospective teachers towards teaching as a profession

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t -value
Male	100	34.89	8.39	199	7.144*
Female	100	42.59	11.77		

Significant at 0.05 level t -value at 0.05 = 2.029

Table 4 shows that the calculated t -value is 7.144 with significant probability value (p-value) of 0.000 calculated at level of significance 0.05. Since the intended p-value of 0.000 is less than alpha level, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that significant differences exist in the attitude of male and female prospective teachers towards teaching as a profession. The statistics reflected that female prospective teachers have positive attitude towards teaching as a profession with mean value of 42.59 than their male prospective teachers' counterpart whose mean value is 34.89.

Discussion

A standout amongst the utmost variables add to understudy achievement is the instructor and teaching quality. It is very much recorded that a spurred, conferred and qualified instructor can contribute massively towards understudies' enhanced learning results. As per the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, Pakistan would need to enlist another 523,100 teachers by 2030 if targets like widespread essential and auxiliary "quality" education plot in the Sustainable Development Goals are to be accomplished. Taking a glimpse at the measurements, Pakistan is probably going to have a lack of qualified teachers later on in light of the fact that not exclusively is a tremendous segment of the present teaching power getting more seasoned. The potential work advertise likewise does not see the teaching profession as a first-decision vocation alternative.

In Pakistan, if any one met with some youthful teachers to check whether teaching was their favoured profession and in the event that they would settle on it again if allowed to pick their vocation choices. All respondents said that they had "arrived" into the profession rather than effectively picking it and given another opportunity; they would pick an alternate profession. Being a teacher is regularly an impermanent course of action in Pakistan until the time a superior open door comes thumping. Given this, one can without much of a stretch comprehend the dedication and inspiration that teachers would have towards their understudies. Social esteem is an overwhelming element contributes towards a change of profession, as said by various respondents. The low eminence connected to teaching is an issue that has been viewed as minor previously. Considering the lack of quality teachers, it is critical that approaches are embraced at the administration level to draw in equipped individuals towards the profession. Individuals should be offered vocation and professional advancement openings that in any event live up to their desires, if not surpass them.

The multiplicities of educational issues that exist in Pakistan are put on the shoulders of teachers. Without a doubt, there are great deals of issues that exist in the Pakistani education system yet is it reasonable for place all the fault on the nation's teachers? Tragically, the talk on education inside the nation ascribes to teachers everything that isn't right with the system. In any case, don't we have to hear the teachers themselves before we achieve any excellent conclusions? We have heard a considerable measure about teacher non-attendance and a few teachers evading work yet have we heard the records of a great many other people who are committed to their employments and appear to class in grim conditions each day? We can barbecue them unendingly for the low learning results in students yet we don't stop to consider bestowing quality preparing to them. With no idea to their expert improvement, do we truly know anything about the teachers' own impression of the occupations they set out to do each morning? A response to these inquiries will just indicate the multifaceted inadequacies inside our system, which come up short our teachers consistently.

As per numerous empirical studies, the poor learning results of Pakistani students are a consequence of systemic disappointments and teachers alone can't be rebuked for these. One of the real reasons is that teaching calling is not generously compensated, all around perceived, and very much secured calling. Many capable people don't come in teaching field due to these concerns. The study results indicated that prospective male and female teachers from rural and urban areas have negative attitude towards teaching as a career. Teaching is an all comer activity, far from being a decent job- which anybody only does when other serious engagements are yet available. Likewise, the position of these undergraduate education students corroborates that of Okemakinde, et al (2013) who asserted that practicing teacher and colleges of education showed lack of interest toward teaching. In Pakistan there is no much regard to teaching profession that could afford its members various opportunities like official car, well-furnished office with secretary, clerk, typist, vehicle loan, housing loan, overseas trip, etc., most of which are being denied teaching profession especially at primary and secondary school levels.

Recognized as engagement and excitement is pivotal for high school victory and contributes to scholarly accomplishment. Kirpatrick (2007) characterized work engagement as the intrigued of a representative in passion for, and speculation within the work put (Rajagopalan, K., 2009). Advance, they portrayed commitments as vitality, engagement, and adequacy. In any case, this definition contrasts from that of Schaufeil et al. who characterized engagement within the classroom as a positive, work-related state of intellect characterized by vigor, devotion and assimilation.

In their school strategies, instructors are more stressed that learners are locked in educating and stressed almost the quality of education they give. Marzano (2003) portrayed that instructors locked in are seeking out for new concepts, actualizing best educating strategies, altering learners taking duty for understudy learning, checking understudy advance commonly and giving input to learners. Instructors who have favourable states of mind towards their work and think within the centrality of the instructive handle are more likely to take part in exercises associated with more prominent instructor commitment, hence having an advantageous impact on the mental conditions of their learners and encouraging understudy engagement within the school setting, Fabric and Strategy. (Robert J. Marzano., et at, 2003).

State of mind of Instructor Understanding state of mind is imperative for understanding human behaviour. In an instructive setting, comprehending teacher's states of mind that impact their behaviour in classroom is pivotal. It is instructors that decide the yield of the instructive framework of a country. The part of an educator is greatly crucial for advancement to a society since as it were instructors, they executing most

recent data, in arrange to the understudies in a formal classroom setting. Hence, the yield of a country's directions framework will be decided by his identity, character and commitment to the calling of instructors. No question that within the advancement of the country educating may be a calling that plays an imperative part. Educating calling incorporates data transmission of data and abilities to the following. The educator is the most excellent part show of their understudies. So, it is the extraordinary duty of an educator to deliver coordinate extension and headway into understudies when they got to be important individuals and great human being of the nation. Dufour expressed that as it were the individual who called instructors that influences the economy of any nation and future of their understudies. They construct on student's earlier information and data, life encounters, teacher eagerness for fulfils instructive targets. Instructors enthusiastically lock in their understudies inside and athwart subject matter parts in issue fathoming and basic considering. The obligation of an educator is to assist and direct understudies to induce superior understanding almost teach and to mean morals with our collective objectives and instructive legacy.

A great instructor, as seen by the understudies, sets up positive interpersonal connections, give structure without being as well inflexible, and make learning fun. To capture these abilities, great instructors must really commit themselves to the understudies, classroom, and directions substance. Questions at that point emerge as to what is the commitment, how it has been considered within the past, and why it is so crucial for instructors to have. Concurring to the creators in, commitment to work is considered a fundamental develop of work fulfilment and is essentially related with labour efficiency. Educator commitment in all shapes may be a pivotal figure in deciding results for instructors. Instructors who are less committed make fewer plans to move forward the quality of their educating. The lower level of commitment among instructors may make a predicament that may influence the instructive organization adversely and may cause instructors to be less effective in their proficient execution or to take off the calling. Building on this, the creators in clarified that commitment pushes instructors to seek for superior instructing strategies, indeed when understudies display negative states of mind or challenging behaviour. More critical educator commitment moreover emphatically impacts understudies through expanded understudy engagements. Instructors these days have been battling to keep pace with the dynamism of the society alongside the different issues confronted by open schools. With these escalating demands and new challenges inalienable within the current educational climate, what it implies to be a committed instructor is additionally changing. A better level of commitment is anticipated from instructors to manage with the changing educational modules. In any case, such expectation is troublesome to attain without the near reflection of the teachers' sentiments, convictions, and activities, which comprises their state of mind. State of mind is a dynamic component of human identity. It could be an inclination to respond in a certain way towards a planned lesson of boosts. In educating, reasoning is a fundamental concept in understanding the teachers' thought forms, classroom hones, alter, and learning to educate. A teacher's convictions, encounters, and discernments have a more significant impact on their educating hones. It is appearing as a proficient work involves a positive demeanour or behaviours. A teacher's positive demeanours towards work advance superior work impacts, such as work fulfilment and a littler crave to leave from work. Additionally, the state of mind of an instructor towards his calling may be a vital angle that makes a difference one to feel committed in his work. Proficient educator with positive states of mind and commitment are enthusiastic in their career, and it brings them more noteworthy fulfilment. Shockingly, numerous instructors of the display day don't appear to show honest to goodness intrigued in their calling. They proceed to work as it were as mechanical wage earners. They appear to require to educating not since of any venture and enjoying towards the work but since of their failure to secure employment elsewhere. Essentially, those who have been within the calling for a few a long time appear to lose their energy towards what they are doing as reflected on the quality of their execution and state of mind within the working environment. They make less plans to lock in proficient advancement exercises, which are fundamental for them to progress the quality of their educating. Hence, putting into peril the accomplishment of the organization's objective of quality instruction. States of mind and commitment are two critical concepts that must be completely caught on due to its near affiliation with concepts such as inspiration, the organizational culture of the school, and the students' state of mind and learning results. It is for this reason that the analyst, being a school head, got to be fascinated by deciding the teachers' full of feeling demeanour and its impact on their level of commitment within the setting of schools. Furthermore, Izuagba and Obiefula (2005) argued that the social states of teachers have made many to be ashamed of the profession and this has equally made teachers to opt out or supplement teaching with other jobs like teaching, transportation among other (Leu, Elizabeth., 2005). Hence, most of the professional trained teachers are unwilling to remain in teaching while those in training are also not favourable disposed to teaching as a profession. How would a teacher trainee, whose attitude towards teaching as a profession is negative, be highly motivated and efficient; how would the spirit of enquiring and creativity and his commitment to teaching profession be enhanced in him/her? If not, then the huge funds invested on their training by the nation would be a colossal waste. Area wise difference was also revealed in the study is that significant difference exists in the attitude rural area's prospective teachers and urban area's prospective teachers. The rural area's prospective teachers showed positive attitude toward teaching as a profession than urban area's prospective teachers

Significant gender difference was also revealed in the study in terms of the attitude of male and female prospective teachers towards teaching as a profession in favor of female prospective teachers. The outcomes showed that female prospective teachers have significant constructive attitude toward teaching as a profession than their male counterpart. These findings are paralleled with the study of Izuabga and Obiefuna (2005) who said that teaching has been feminized, and in a patriarchal society as ours, women's job is never regarded. Unlike, outcomes of present study contrasts with Leu (2005) who asserts that prospective teachers have not significant differences (Shaheen, F., et al., 2017)

Most noticeable components are lack of employer stability, appropriate social acknowledgment, good salary, and fascination of job. It is difficult to envision the low salaries of teachers in Pakistan. Teachers are the basis of the universal development and they merit preferable salaries over what the originator has revealed. In USA they pay around 4 lakh salary to an instructor for each month. In Pakistan, the salary ought to be set at 40000 rupees least. We cannot expect advance without great teachers and with great salaries numerous brilliant individuals will get to be teachers.

Conclusion

1. Majority of prospective teachers was dissatisfied with teaching as profession.
2. Majority of females was much pleased with teaching with profession as compared to males.
3. Majority of rural area's prospective teachers was much pleased with teaching with profession as paralleled to prospective teachers belonging to urban areas.

Recommendations

1. According to the ILO/UNESCO's proposals, teachers' salaries ought to: a) Reflect the significance to society of the teaching capacity and consequently the significance of teachers, and in addition the obligations of different sorts which fall upon them now and again of their entrance into, administration. b) Compare positively with salaries paid in different occupations, requiring comparative or proportional capabilities. Great salary and all-around perceived status is required for teaching profession generally this profession will bring about maintenance and occupation fulfilment. Salary is imperative on the off chance that it is much appealing to approaching teachers it would upgrade their mentality toward teaching as a profession. In the event that we not offer need to great salary then consider: Do we need teaching to be a "profession" that gives better than average returns and can pull in individuals to it? On the other hand, do we need just those individuals who have no contrasting options to wind up teachers? What's more, do we need them to be poor regardless of being utilized fulltime? While admitting students in teacher education programme, should be based not only on marks but also on the possession of positive attitude towards motivation for teaching with sound moral status, creativity, positive self-concept and a genuine concern for teaching as a profession.

2. Reason for occupational stress for teachers is to be deficient in of sustain they obtain in schools. Numerous foreign schools now provide counselling to guarantee the emotional well-being of teachers, but for Pakistani professors, there is not any type of possibility. Teachers should be free from job stress to work for excellence.

3. Incentives and award of scholarship to students getting admission in teacher training institutes may be given as to improve their attitude toward teaching as a profession. Also, teaching practice allowance should be paid to students of teacher education programmes as their counterparts in other faculties enjoy.

4. Teaching is also a noble profession as it is profession of prophets. Value reorientation to the prospective teachers' students may be given about teaching profession. It will enhance their commitment toward teaching as a profession for money is not an answer to everything.

<http://ijeredefoundations.com.ng/submit-papers>.

References

- Andy Kirkpatrick, *World Englishes: Implications for international communication and English language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2007. Pp. x, 257. Hb \$39.00. *Language in Society*, 38(4), 537-538. doi:10.1017/S0047404509990376
- Cheema, S. and K. Mehmood. 1997. Appraisal Report of Training of Teacher Educators of GCEs under ICF Programmer of Training Project. Provincial Institute of Teacher Education Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan.
- Farooq, R. A. 1994. Education System in Pakistan: Issues and Problems, Asia Society for Promotion of Innovation and Reform in Education, Islamabad, Pakistan.
- Field, A. (2009). *Discovering statistics using SPSS*. USA: Sage publications. Gage, L. N. 1983. *Hand Book of Research on Teaching*. Rand McNally and Company, Chicago, USA.
- Govt. of Pakistan. 1977. *Teacher Education in Pakistan*. Ministry of Education. Curriculum Wing, Islamabad.

- Leu E. 2005. The role of teachers, schools, and communities in quality education: A Review of the Literature. Working Paper No. 1. Academy for Educational Development, Global Education Centre. 1825 Connecticut Ave. NW, Washington, DC 20009-5721.
- Ogunyinka, E. K., Okeke, T. I., & Adedoyin, R. C. (2015). Teacher education and development in Nigeria: An analysis of reforms, challenges and prospects. *Education Journal*, 4(3), 111- 122.
- Okemakinde, T., Alabi, C. O., & Adewuyi, J. O. (2013). The place of teacher in national development in Nigeria. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 19(1), 963-980.
- Okemakinde, T., Adewuyi, J. O., and Alabi, C. O. 2013. The Place of Teacher in National Development in Nigeria. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* Vol. 19, No.1, 2013.
- Pakistan Educational Conference. (1983). Proceedings of the Pakistan Educational Conference, held at Karachi, from 27th November to 1st December 1947. Islamabad: Govt. of Pakistan, Ministry of the Interior, Education Division.
- Robert J. Marzano, Jana S. Marzano and Debra J. Pickering. Classroom Management That Works: Research-Based Strategies for Every Teacher (ASCD, 2003).
- Shaheen, F., Kashif, M. F., Daud, H., & Tariq, M. 2017. Exploring the Attitude of Prospective Teachers towards Teaching Profession. *The Sindh University Journal of Education-SUJE*, 45(2), 2016.
- Sharif, S. M., Ministry of Education, Gov. of Pakistan., & Pakistan. (1960). Report of the Commission on National Education, Ministry of Education, Govt. of Pakistan, - Jan.-August 1959. Karachi: Manager of Publ.
- Siddiqui, S. A. 1970. Taaleem-o-Tarbiat-e-Asatiza. Anjuman-e-Fazleen. Institute of Education and Research, University of the Punjab, Lahore.
- Siddiqui, B. H. 1986. Education: An Islamic Perspective. University Grant Commission, Islamabad.
- Zuagba A. C, Obiefuna, C.A. 2005. Issues and trends in teacher education. Owerri: Cel Bez Publishing.
- Rajagopalan, K. (2009)..

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